

European Central Hub of FS Labs

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European Central Hub of FS Labs

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Author(s)	Lorenza Liroso, Ariane Voyatzakis, Hugo de Vries, Concha Avila, Gabriela Alcat, Daniele Rossi, Elisabetta Pierantoni

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Contributors

Name	Organization
Lorenza Lirosi	FoodDrinkEurope
Ariane Voyatzakis	ANIA
Hugo de Vries	INRAE
Matteo Sabini	EUFIC
Gabriela Versteeg	EFFoST
Anne-Luise Skov Jensen	AU
Daniele Rossi, Elisabetta Pierantoni, Davide Esposito, Tancredi Marini	Confagricoltura
Concha Avila, Gabriela Alcat, Juan Martínez	FIAB
Participants of the Budapest RIPE Workshop, 4/12/2024	FOODPathS consortium, partner networks, Advisory Board and SCAR SWG FS.

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Executive summary

The FOODPathS Knowledge Hub aims to foster collaboration, research, innovation, and practical solutions for Europe's food systems. As a key part of the FOODPathS project, the Knowledge Hub seeks to connect researchers, policymakers, industry leaders, and education to address challenges and drive progress toward sustainable, resilient, and equitable food systems.

Deliverable 4.2 outlines the development, objectives, and achievements of the Knowledge Hub, designed as a centralized platform to connect different stakeholders. Key activities have included mapping Food Systems Living Labs across Europe, identifying best practices, and developing scalable models that can be applied regionally and globally. These efforts have led to the development of a platform designed to facilitate knowledge exchange, foster collaboration, and drive innovation. Input from stakeholders through a survey and workshop has been essential in shaping the platform's structure and ensuring it meets user needs.

Collaboration with National Food Technology Platforms (NFTPs) plays an essential role in the Knowledge Hub's strategy. By drawing on NFTPs' networks and expertise, the Hub will address diverse regional priorities, build cross-border partnerships, and promote innovative solutions. This approach ensures the platform is inclusive, adaptable, scaleable, and relevant for tackling issues such as climate resilience, digital innovation, and food security.

The finalized Knowledge Hub's prototype will be presented at the [FOODPathS Festival](#) in May 2025, offering a chance to showcase its features, gather additional feedback, and refine its operations. The Knowledge Hub is set to become a valuable resource for connecting stakeholders and supporting sustainable food system transitions across Europe, linking local initiatives to broader global objectives.

INTRODUCTION

This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the progress, strategic development, and foundational work undertaken to establish the Knowledge Hub, a key initiative under Work Package 4 (WP4) of the FOODPathS project. The Knowledge Hub is envisioned as a transformative platform aimed at uniting stakeholders across Europe's food systems to foster collaboration, drive innovation, and accelerate the transition toward sustainability, resilience, and equity.

At its core, the Knowledge Hub aims to bridge research, innovation, policy and education to provide an integrated, user-centred platform to address the multiple challenges facing today's food systems and to create a collaborative space for interdisciplinary research, co-creation and knowledge exchange.

Activities under WP4 have concentrated on mapping FS-LLs across Europe, identifying best practices, and actively engaging stakeholders through targeted surveys and interactive workshops. These efforts have provided critical input for shaping the structure and functionalities of the Knowledge Hub, ensuring its design reflects its users' specific needs and expectations. Central to its development are principles of inclusivity, accessibility, and adaptability, ensuring the platform evolves in response to emerging trends and challenges in the food systems landscape.

A defining element of the Knowledge Hub is its collaboration with National Food Technology Platforms (NFTPs), which play a pivotal role in promoting regional engagement and fostering cross-border partnerships. By integrating local and regional perspectives, NFTPs create an interconnected ecosystem that supports innovation, scales successful models, and aligns diverse efforts across the European food system.

This deliverable highlights the Knowledge Hub's conceptual framework, the insights gained from stakeholder engagements, and the proposed tools and features, such as the Knowledge Hub Startup Award, that exemplify its potential for fostering innovation and sustainability. Additionally, the report outlines the Hub's alignment with the RIPE framework (Research, Innovation, Policy, and Education), emphasizing its role as a driving force for systemic transformation within European food systems.

Looking ahead, the Knowledge Hub will reach another significant milestone with the unveiling of its enhanced prototype at the [FOODPathS Festival](#) in May 2025. Initially presented at [SIAL Paris on October 21, 2024](#), this second showcase will provide an opportunity to highlight improvements, demonstrate expanded functionalities, and gather further stakeholder feedback to refine its role in supporting collaborative efforts to reshape food systems across Europe.

This deliverable captures the progress made thus far and charts a path for the continued development and evolution of the Knowledge Hub. It underscores the importance of collaborative, interdisciplinary, and innovative approaches to tackling the complex challenges of the European food system and illustrates the Hub's potential as a cornerstone for driving impactful and lasting change.

1. European Knowledge Hub

The European Knowledge Hub, developed under the FOODPathS initiative, is a transformative endeavor to unite stakeholders across the food system value chain to address current and future challenges. This innovative Hub fosters collaboration, accelerates innovation, and promotes sustainable solutions by serving as a centralized space for interaction, knowledge exchange, and capacity-building.

The Knowledge Hub aspires to be a cornerstone in transforming Europe's food systems by achieving the following objectives:

- **Unite stakeholders:** The Knowledge Hub creates a network of interconnected actors, including producers, manufacturers, researchers, policymakers, and consumers. By fostering dialogue and collaboration among these diverse groups, the Hub enables holistic problem-solving and co-creation of impactful solutions tailored to address the complex challenges modern food systems face.

- **Facilitate collaboration:** At the heart of its mission lies the facilitation of cross-regional and cross-sectoral partnerships. The Knowledge Hub provides a virtual space for stakeholders from different disciplines and geographies to collaborate. This inclusive approach ensures that solutions are comprehensive, contextually relevant, and applicable across various food system scenarios.
- **Promote innovation:** Leveraging successful research and innovation (R&I) practices from across Europe, the Knowledge Hub acts as a catalyst for scaling proven solutions. Offering access to cutting-edge knowledge, technologies, and methodologies accelerates the adoption of innovative approaches that drive sustainability throughout the food system.
- **Enhance knowledge exchange:** The Knowledge Hub provides a dynamic repository of best practices, case studies, tools, and methodologies. Living Labs and stakeholders can share insights, learn from others' experiences, and adapt successful approaches to their unique contexts, creating a continuous cycle of improvement and innovation across the network.
- **Promote sustainability:** The Knowledge Hub prioritizes environmental sustainability, circular practices, and public health improvements. Focusing on these critical areas aims to contribute to a resilient, future-ready food system that meets societal needs while preserving the planet's resources.
- **Support education and training:** Recognizing the need to address skills gaps in the food system, the Knowledge Hub could connect Living Labs and other stakeholders with educational initiatives such as the Pact for Skills¹ initiative. By integrating training programs and fostering stronger links between industry and academia, the Hub would help equip the workforce with the necessary skills to drive innovation and sustainability. Additionally, it could align with potential forthcoming Partnerships to further enhance capacity-building efforts within the food sector. The Pact for Skills, launched by the European Commission, serves as a key reference point in this context, promoting upskilling and reskilling initiatives that the Knowledge Hub could complement and support.
- **Strengthen public-private partnerships:** The Knowledge Hub emphasizes the importance of synergies between industry and research to foster impactful change. It acts as a bridge, aligning public and private sector efforts to ensure that innovations translate into real-world solutions with measurable impacts.

The Knowledge Hub's value lies in its ability to act as a catalyst for transformation within Europe's food systems by delivering:

- **Knowledge sharing:** The Hub facilitates the dynamic exchange of information, enabling Living Labs and stakeholders to learn from each other, share best practices, and adapt methodologies to local and regional contexts.
- **Scaling innovations:** By identifying and disseminating successful practices, the Knowledge Hub bridges the gap between localized initiatives and continental strategies, promoting region-specific solutions that can be implemented on a broader scale.
- **Cross-border collaboration:** The Knowledge Hub enriches solutions with diverse perspectives and shared resources by linking national and regional initiatives. This fosters innovation and ensures that approaches benefit from a broader pool of expertise.
- **Strengthening the Food System ecosystem:** The Knowledge Hub builds a resilient ecosystem of stakeholders committed to sustainable transformation. This collaborative environment ensures long-term adaptability and supports developing a robust food system.

2. Foodtech Living Labs Platform

The [Foodtech Living Labs Platform](#), launched during a dedicated session at [SIAL Paris on October 21, 2024](#), marks a significant milestone in developing the European Knowledge Hub. This platform is a central node designed to connect and empower stakeholders across Europe's food tech ecosystem. Emerging from a comprehensive mapping and review of Food Systems Living Labs across Europe, the platform identifies successful models that can be scaled and adapted to address diverse challenges

¹ The [Pact for Skills](#) is one of the flagship actions of the European Skills Agenda. The Pact aims to support public and private organisations with upskilling and reskilling, so they can thrive through the green and digital transitions.

within the food system. These Living Labs function as dynamic, collaborative environments where research intersects with practice, fostering partnerships between diverse stakeholders such as food manufacturers, farmers, retailers, technology providers, and policymakers. Operating at national, regional, and local levels, FS-Labs are instrumental in addressing key issues, including²:

- **Environmental sustainability:** Developing solutions to reduce environmental impact and promote regenerative practices.
- **Circular economy practices:** Advancing resource efficiency and waste reduction.
- **Nutrition and health:** Innovating to improve public health and food security.
- **Food security:** Addressing systemic vulnerabilities to ensure resilient supply chains.
- **Digital innovation:** Leveraging technology to enhance processes and transparency across the value chain.
- **Empowering citizens and communities**

The **Foodtech Living Labs Platform** aims to connect these FS labs across Europe, facilitating the exchange of knowledge, proven practices, and innovative methodologies. By creating an interconnected innovation network, the platform ensures that successful solutions can be scaled and adapted to suit diverse regional and national contexts, fostering resilience and sustainability within the food system.

This platform is a foundational step towards the broader Knowledge Hub, integrating insights and fostering collaborations that span the entire food system value chain. Emphasizing co-creation and stakeholder engagement bridges gaps between industry, academia, and policymakers, driving tangible change and actionable outcomes.

The platform is designed to allow the integration of additional Living Labs and case studies as it evolves. While it currently serves as a starting point, its potential for expansion ensures that the Knowledge Hub can continually adapt to emerging needs and opportunities within the food system. This iterative approach ensures relevance, inclusivity, and impact as the platform becomes a comprehensive tool for driving transformation. Also, it will then present the richness, diversity and innovativeness of European's R&I activities in the food domain.

By laying this foundation, the Foodtech Living Labs Platform exemplifies the power of collaboration, innovation, and sustainability. It connects stakeholders and creates a vibrant ecosystem that empowers them to tackle the most pressing challenges of our food systems.

Figure 1 - Foodtech Living Labs Platform screenshot (Source: www.foodpaths.eu)

² These issues correspond well with the four priorities defined within the FOOD2030 agenda, H2020 and Horizon Europe (HE) Framework programs; hence FS Labs may be considered in further supporting projects financed by HE.

Figure 2- Seven dominant-orientations for food system cases operating at five different scales³.

3. Role of National Food Technology Platforms in the Knowledge Hub

The National Food Technology Platforms (NFTPs) are essential networks within the European agri-food ecosystem, serving as pivotal connectors between public and private stakeholders, including academia, industry, research institutions, and policymakers. Since their inception, NFTPs have played a crucial role in fostering collaboration at the national level to address critical food system challenges and promote sustainable innovations. Tailored to the specific needs of their respective countries or regions, NFTPs share a unified mission: advancing research, innovation, and education to strengthen the agri-food sector.

By closely collaborating with the [European Technology Platform \(ETP\) Food for Life](#), NFTPs ensure the alignment of national priorities with overarching European objectives. This collaboration transforms localized challenges into actionable insights, enabling solutions to be adapted and scaled across Europe. The role of NFTPs is central to the success of the Knowledge Hub. Their contributions ensure that the Hub remains relevant to diverse local contexts while fostering cross-border and cross-sectoral collaborations. Acting as ambassadors, NFTPs leverage their extensive networks to promote the Knowledge Hub within their respective countries, enhancing its visibility and encouraging participation. This localized approach ensures that the platform incorporates a wide range of perspectives and expertise.

NFTPs bring valuable insights from regional initiatives, highlighting best practices, successful models, and lessons learned. These contributions enrich the Knowledge Hub's content and functionality, enabling the identification of innovative solutions that can be adapted and implemented across different regions. As intermediaries between national and European levels, NFTPs are uniquely positioned to facilitate cross-border collaborations, fostering the exchange of ideas, resources, and expertise. This approach helps create solutions that are regionally tailored yet broadly applicable, amplifying the Knowledge Hub's impact and reach.

Aligned with the Knowledge Hub's objectives, NFTPs strengthen the platform's ability to:

- **Promote sustainability** by integrating region-specific innovations that address environmental, social, and economic challenges.
- **Foster innovation** through access to cutting-edge research and co-creation among diverse stakeholders.
- **Build resilience** in food systems by supporting multi-sectoral and multi-regional partnerships to tackle complex challenges collaboratively.

³ It should be noted that cases may have multiple orientations and operate across scales. Modified from the source: [de Vries et al., 2023, H, Donner M, Fabiano F, Mamès M, Lazaro-Mojica J, Cotillas E, Avila C, Martínez J, Alcat G, Rossi D, Pierantoni E, Marini T, Bruen A, Vordemfelde J, Amorese V, Lirosi L and Voyatzakis A \(2024\) Co-creation in partnerships contributing to the sustainability of food systems: insights from 52 case studies in Europe. Front. Sustain. Food Syst. 8:1399275.](#)

By promoting the Knowledge Hub, sharing regional insights, and facilitating collaborations, NFTPs ensure the platform remains dynamic, inclusive, and responsive to stakeholders' needs across Europe. Their involvement bridges local actions with global objectives, reinforcing the Knowledge Hub's mission as a unifying platform for sustainable food system innovation. As of January 2025, the governance of the NFTPs in Spain, Austria, and Italy includes support for the Food4All Partnership proposal, a public-private EU initiative under Cluster 6 of the FP10 framework programme. This initiative aims to leverage innovation investments, not only from large companies but also from SMEs and the primary sector, following a bottom-up approach that respects regional cultures, traditions, landscapes, and territorial values within the EU agri-food system.

Through these efforts, NFTPs play a crucial role in driving impactful change across every level of the agri-food value chain.

4. Stakeholder engagement in developing the Knowledge Hub

Effective stakeholder engagement is crucial in the development of the Knowledge Hub to ensure that it meets the diverse needs and expectations of its users. By actively involving stakeholders, the Knowledge Hub can become a dynamic, user-driven platform that fosters collaboration and innovation in sustainable food systems.

4.1. Survey insights

To gather meaningful insights, a [survey](#) targeting Living Labs and private sector stakeholders was launched through social media. This survey aims to identify key needs, expectations, and desired functionalities of the Knowledge Hub. The findings will play a pivotal role in shaping the platform to ensure it aligns with the practical requirements of its users (*For the survey, see Annex I*).

The survey is structured to address key areas critical for the development and functionality of the Knowledge Hub. It includes questions designed to identify the most valuable resources for stakeholders, such as case studies, research databases, networking opportunities, training materials, policy guidelines, and digital collaboration tools. These insights will guide the selection of content and features the platform offers.

Additionally, the survey seeks to pinpoint priority areas within sustainable food systems that stakeholders find most urgent, such as innovation, education and training, governance, entrepreneurship, and climate resilience. These focus areas will help shape the strategic direction of the Knowledge Hub.

Stakeholder preferences for engagement are another important component of the survey. Questions are included to understand how users would like to interact with the platform, whether through webinars, accessing resources, joining forums, or contributing their expertise. These responses will inform the platform's design and user interaction strategies.

Finally, the survey includes an open-ended section inviting stakeholders to propose ideas for how the Knowledge Hub can provide unique value, ensuring the platform remains innovative and relevant to the needs of its users.

The survey will act as a cornerstone for developing the Knowledge Hub, ensuring that its strategic framework and functionality align with its users' practical needs and expectations. The survey aims to collect valuable insights reflecting real-world challenges and opportunities within the food system by directly engaging with Living Labs and private sector stakeholders. This process highlights the importance of stakeholder involvement and reinforces the commitment to creating a user-centric platform.

The Knowledge Hub's ultimate goal is to foster an ecosystem that promotes collaboration, knowledge-sharing, and innovation. Through the survey, stakeholders are invited to contribute their perspectives on key priorities, preferred modes of engagement, and the most beneficial resources. These contributions will help shape a practical and forward-thinking platform, addressing the food system's diverse needs while facilitating meaningful connections across sectors.

By leveraging the insights gained from the survey, the Knowledge Hub will emerge as a dynamic and responsive tool capable of driving sustainable innovation and fostering collaboration at all levels of the food value chain.

Primary results

Part 1: Understanding Your Needs

The first section of the survey focused on identifying the specific resources and tools that stakeholders would find most valuable in the Knowledge Hub. Respondents expressed a strong interest in a variety of resources, reflecting the diverse challenges and priorities within the food systems community.

The findings from this part of the survey underscore the multifaceted needs of stakeholders engaging with the Knowledge Hub. The Hub's development must prioritize providing a comprehensive suite of resources that includes networking opportunities, digital collaboration tools, training programs, policy support, and practical case studies. By addressing these diverse requirements, the Knowledge Hub can position itself as a valuable asset for stakeholders across the food system value chain.

One of the most frequently mentioned needs was the availability of **networking opportunities**. Stakeholders emphasized the importance of connecting with other actors across the food system, including industry players, policymakers, researchers, and educators. These connections are seen as crucial for fostering collaboration, exchanging ideas, and building partnerships that drive innovation and systemic change.

Digital tools were highlighted as a critical component of the Knowledge Hub. Respondents expressed interest in platforms that enable real-time communication, knowledge sharing, and co-creation. Such tools are expected to streamline cross-sectoral collaboration and facilitate joint problem-solving efforts, particularly for geographically dispersed stakeholders.

Capacity building was another key area of interest. Many participants indicated that training resources tailored to food system challenges would be highly beneficial. Suggested topics included sustainability practices, policy navigation, and the application of digital innovations in food production and distribution. The need for clear and actionable **policy guidance** emerged as a priority. Stakeholders highlighted the value of having access to recommendations and insights that could support their decision-making processes and help align their practices with evolving regulations and sustainability goals.

Respondents expressed a strong preference for access to **case studies** showcasing successful projects and best practices. These real-world examples were seen as a source of inspiration and practical guidance, offering lessons that could be adapted and implemented in other contexts to address similar challenges.

The responses revealed a broad range of interests, with several recurring themes indicating stakeholders' shared priorities for systemic transformation.

The survey responses indicate that the Knowledge Hub must adopt a multifaceted approach to addressing sustainable food systems. By prioritizing innovation, governance, education, climate resilience, and entrepreneurship, the Hub can cater to the diverse needs of its stakeholders and serve as a catalyst for systemic change in the food sector.

A significant portion of respondents highlighted the need for the Knowledge Hub to focus on **fostering innovation and integrating advanced technologies** into food systems. This includes the development of digital tools, precision agriculture techniques, and novel processing methods that enhance efficiency, reduce waste, and support sustainability.

Policy and governance emerged as another critical area for the Knowledge Hub. Stakeholders emphasized the importance of providing resources that support the development and implementation of effective policies, including frameworks that promote sustainability, align with global and regional goals, and address regulatory challenges.

Education and capacity building were consistently identified as priority areas. Respondents stressed the need for the Knowledge Hub to provide accessible training programs, workshops, and educational materials tailored to various actors in the food system. These resources should aim to enhance skills, raise awareness of sustainability issues, and support the adoption of best practices.

Climate resilience and environmental sustainability were frequently mentioned as top priorities. Participants noted the urgency of addressing issues such as climate change adaptation, resource efficiency, biodiversity preservation, and reducing the environmental footprint of food systems. The Knowledge Hub is seen as a platform that can facilitate the dissemination of strategies and practices to enhance resilience and sustainability.

Entrepreneurship and business development were also highlighted as important areas for the Knowledge Hub. Respondents expressed the need for tools and guidance to support startups, small and medium enterprises, and other innovators in scaling up sustainable business models and addressing market challenges.

Part 2: Expectations for the Knowledge Hub

Survey participants highlighted several preferred methods of engagement with the Knowledge Hub, reflecting a strong demand for interactivity and accessibility. Across responses, interactive webinars and online workshops emerged as a top choice, emphasizing the need for real-time knowledge sharing and collaborative learning. Participation in forums or discussion groups was also frequently mentioned, indicating the importance of providing spaces for dialogue and exchange among stakeholders.

Respondents expressed interest in contributing their own knowledge and experiences, underscoring the value of a participatory approach that allows users to enrich the Hub's content. Additionally, the importance of access to downloadable resources and regular newsletters or updates was highlighted, suggesting that stakeholders value a combination of dynamic and static engagement options to stay informed and connected.

When asked what would make the Knowledge Hub stand out and provide unique value, respondents provided thoughtful and innovative suggestions:

- Participants stressed the importance of **breaking down silos** between agriculture, food production, and biotechnology markets. This integration is seen as a critical step in enabling actionable “One Health” approaches that address interconnected challenges in health, sustainability, and food systems.
- A recurring recommendation was the **inclusion of diverse materials** related to understanding and transforming food systems. Respondents suggested that the Knowledge Hub should encompass research, case studies, guidelines, and other formats in all EU languages, making it a truly inclusive and comprehensive resource.
- To enhance usability, stakeholders emphasized the **need for robust filtering tools**. Suggested filters include country, thematic focus area, stakeholder types involved, resource type (e.g., research, case study, self-reported guidelines), and more. This level of categorization would allow users to quickly find relevant information tailored to their needs.

4.2. Workshop insights

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Figure 3 - FOODPathS workshop, Budapest, 3-4 December 2024

To advance the development of the Knowledge Hub and ensure its functionalities align with stakeholder needs, a dedicated workshop titled “*The Knowledge Hub of Food System Labs: Uniting R&I, Science-to-Policy, and Education (RIPE)*” was held on December 4, 2024, as part of the FOODPathS event in Budapest (see **Annex II** for more details), preceding the FOOD2030 event of the EC, Hungarian Presidency and BioEAST. With **43 participants** from diverse sectors across the food system value chain, the workshop represented a pivotal opportunity to gather direct feedback and actionable recommendations from stakeholders representing various food system value chain sectors.

The primary objective of the workshop was to validate the Knowledge Hub's conceptual framework, ensuring it addresses key challenges and leverages opportunities within European food systems. Discussions focused on identifying synergies and gaps in integrating research, innovation, policy, and education to enhance the platform's relevance and impact. By fostering co-creation, the workshop aimed to encourage stakeholders to collaboratively explore functionalities, collaboration models, and tools that could improve the Hub's inclusivity and effectiveness.

The workshop featured interactive group discussions and participatory exercises, which provided a structured environment for exploring how key orientations, such as research, policy, education, entrepreneurship, and observatory functions, could be better integrated within the Knowledge Hub. Participants evaluated the alignment between these areas, identifying opportunities for synergy and addressing areas of divergence to strengthen the Hub's ability to drive systemic transformation across the food system.

A central outcome of the workshop was the collection of detailed input on prototyping recommendations for the Knowledge Hub's next developmental phases. This feedback will inform refinements to the current framework and guide the creation of a roadmap for future enhancements, ensuring the platform evolves into a user-centred, dynamic tool tailored to the needs of stakeholders across Europe. This will become a key element in the future Manual of the Prototype Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems and be presented at the FOODPathS Festival in Brussels in May 2025.

Outputs from the different groups

Group 1 emphasized the need to address the fragmentation and complexity posed by the multitude of existing initiatives in the food systems landscape. Rather than creating entirely new structures, the

Knowledge Hub should focus on consolidating and integrating these initiatives to provide a cohesive and accessible platform. A key recommendation is mapping **best practices** in sustainable food systems, prioritizing areas such as education and innovation. The group highlighted the importance of creating user-friendly communication materials, including videos, leaflets, and awards, to effectively disseminate information and engage stakeholders.

The Knowledge Hub should also serve as a **central repository for European projects**, leveraging categorized criteria from WP3 to organize and present these initiatives effectively. The group suggested hosting an annual meeting to foster collaboration to facilitate networking and knowledge sharing among stakeholders. Beyond this, an **online exchange platform** was proposed to enable the sharing of best practices and ongoing dialogue.

Incorporating an **AI-driven matchmaking interface** was identified as a critical tool to bridge the gap between solution providers, such as universities and research institutions, and end-users, including industry actors and farmers. This interface could facilitate targeted collaborations by aligning expressed needs with innovative solutions. The group also stressed the importance of developing specific guidelines and methodologies to replicate successful concepts locally, ensuring scalability and adaptability.

Group 2 highlighted the potential of the Knowledge Hub as a transformative resource for fostering collaboration and knowledge-sharing within food systems. A key recommendation was mapping **use cases for living labs** that exemplify sustainable food systems. This mapping would provide stakeholders, including citizens, with concrete examples of successful initiatives, serving as a reference and an inspiration for new projects.

The group stressed the importance of ensuring the **Knowledge Hub remains open and accessible to everyone**, enabling a broad spectrum of stakeholders to benefit from its resources. Accessibility was linked to the ease of identifying and connecting with relevant stakeholders, emphasizing the need for streamlined tools to facilitate these connections. The Hub should serve as a platform where users can easily locate peers who have successfully implemented sustainability measures, promoting peer learning and collaboration.

Additionally, the Knowledge Hub was envisioned as a **discovery tool** capable of helping users uncover unknown areas of relevance or opportunities they may not have considered. This aligns with the suggestion to use the Hub as a **nudging tool** in a complex system, guiding users toward meaningful actions and informed decisions. The Knowledge Hub could become an asset for advancing sustainable practices across food systems by simplifying navigation and offering intuitive insights.

Group 3 emphasized several critical resources and tools to enhance the Knowledge Hub's value for stakeholders in food systems. A key recommendation was the implementation of **data-sharing agreements** to foster collaboration among diverse actors. These agreements establish clear guidelines and trust mechanisms, ensuring stakeholders can confidently exchange information and co-create solutions.

Another priority identified was the **wide promotion of the Knowledge Hub** to maximize its accessibility and visibility across the food system landscape. By reaching a broader audience, the Hub could attract more users, facilitate greater collaboration, and ensure its utility is recognized and utilized by diverse stakeholders.

The group also highlighted the need for **structured and actionable data systems, such as dashboards⁴**, to present complex information in an organized, user-friendly format. Dashboards would enable users to quickly access and interpret key data, streamlining decision-making processes and driving evidence-based actions.

Lastly, the group proposed establishing **collaborative platforms** within the Hub to enable seamless knowledge exchange and feedback. These platforms would allow stakeholders to share best practices, discuss challenges, and co-develop innovative solutions, fostering a dynamic and inclusive environment for food system transformation.

⁴ EC-JRC Dashboard :

https://datam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datam/mashup/EU_FOOD_SYSTEM_MONITORING/index.html

5. The Knowledge Hub's role within the RIPE framework

The Knowledge Hub of Food System Labs could serve as a tool in operationalizing the RIPE framework (Research, Innovation, Policy, and Education) by potentially bridging the gap between science, policy, and practice. The way the Hub is structured, in terms of the seven dominant orientations (see Figure 2 above), immediately allows analyzing cases in multiple orientations. The Hub is envisioned as a platform designed to address the complexity and interconnectedness of food systems while fostering collaboration among diverse stakeholders; this will be even possible along different scales. Several key interactions and contributions could illustrate the Hub's potential within the RIPE framework.

Research and innovation: bridging knowledge and practice

The Knowledge Hub could act as a repository for research findings, data, case studies, and proven methodologies, offering researchers and innovators a centralized platform for (up-to-date) knowledge exchange. Participants at the workshop emphasized the importance of mapping best practices and sustainable food system cases to provide a comprehensive foundation for action. The Hub might support actionable research outcomes aligned with real-world challenges by incorporating tools like data-sharing agreements and structured dashboards. Furthermore, matchmaking features within the Hub could connect researchers with industry practitioners, ensuring that innovation addresses the practical needs of food system actors. It should be noted that cases are context-dependent; however, the Hub will clarify which generic knowledge may be more widely used.

Policy: informing and guiding evidence-based decisions

Policymakers might benefit from structured, science-based advice to navigate the complexity of food systems effectively. The Knowledge Hub could be an observatory, offering objective data and conceptual models to guide policy decisions. Even more, the Hub will also be fueled by policy-oriented food system cases that may inspire others. As highlighted during the workshop, the Hub could act as a centralised reference point, providing policymakers with science-based baselines and facilitating scenario analysis through simulations and serious games. These resources could help policymakers understand the implications of their decisions and integrate food system complexity into scalable policies from local to regional and EU levels. Additionally, the Hub's collaborative platforms might enable regular, structured dialogues between regulators, researchers, and educators, fostering cross-sector alignment as well as cross-scale solutions. The latter is of crucial importance for policymakers operating at urban, regional, national, European or inter-continental scales.

Education: empowering change through learning

Education, as a fundamental pillar of the RIPE framework, could be supported by the Knowledge Hub to address skills gaps and promote lifelong learning. Workshop participants suggested integrating citizen science initiatives and serious games into educational strategies to raise awareness and drive behavioural change. The Hub might host webinars, workshops, and training modules tailored to various audiences, including policymakers, industry actors, and educators. By offering guidelines and methodologies for replicating successful practices locally, the Hub could ensure that knowledge is accessible and actionable across all food system levels. It should be noted that aligning with the [Agrifood Pact for Skills](#) activities is imperative. Synergies between education-oriented and R&I-oriented partnerships will strongly influence the transition towards sustainable food systems.

Facilitating systems-level integration

The Knowledge Hub could foster the integration of the RIPE components by creating an ecosystem where research informs policy, innovation drives actionable solutions, and education empowers stakeholders to

adapt to changing conditions. The workshop discussions highlighted the potential importance of collaborative platforms for knowledge exchange, public consultations, and fostering international agreements on shared challenges such as food waste. The Hub's capacity to centralize initiatives, visualize best practices, and encourage cross-sectoral dialogue might ensure that efforts are aligned, inclusive, and sustainable.

The Knowledge Hub within the RIPE framework could act as a dynamic tool for addressing the multifaceted challenges of food systems. By fostering collaboration, disseminating knowledge, and supporting informed decision-making, the Hub might strengthen the foundation for a sustainable, resilient, and inclusive food system across Europe.

6. Tools and features for the Knowledge Hub

The Knowledge Hub is envisioned as a dynamic, user-friendly platform that could foster collaboration, knowledge exchange, and innovation among diverse stakeholders within the food system. By incorporating accessible and interactive tools, the Hub would aim to ensure meaningful engagement and resource sharing among participants, potentially becoming a central resource for transforming food systems.

The Knowledge Hub could prioritize networking as a core functionality by offering matchmaking events and shared contact repositories to connect stakeholders. These features might facilitate the formation of meaningful collaborations among researchers, industry professionals, policymakers, and educators. Interactive tools, such as virtual forums, discussion groups, and live webinars, could provide real-time engagement opportunities, enabling participants to exchange ideas and best practices seamlessly.

To ensure the platform is accessible and useful for a wide audience, the Hub could integrate multiple formats, such as:

- **Virtual collaboration spaces:** These could include virtual meeting rooms, shared workspaces, and discussion forums where users collaborate on documents, hold workshops, and discuss initiatives in real-time. This format would enable geographically dispersed Living Labs to work collaboratively on shared goals.
- **Data repositories:** A centralized library could house case studies of successful projects, research findings, policy guidance, and training resources. This repository might grow continuously, with stakeholders contributing new insights and updates.
- **Downloadable guides and tools:** Easy-to-use resources, such as templates and policy recommendations, could be provided to facilitate stakeholder activities.

Participants might engage with the Knowledge Hub through:

- **Interactive webinars and online workshops:** These events could cover emerging trends, best practices, and cutting-edge research, fostering a culture of learning and adaptation. The Knowledge Hub could organize regular webinars focused on emerging topics and challenges within the food system. These sessions, led by experts from academia, industry, and policy, might facilitate the exchange of ideas, best practices, and innovative solutions. These webinars could address topics such as technological advancements, policy updates, sustainability practices, and educational needs. These events might ensure that the Knowledge Hub remains aligned with the evolving dynamics of the food system, offering stakeholders opportunities to engage, network, and collaboratively address shared challenges.
- **Contributing knowledge and experiences:** Stakeholders could share their expertise, enriching the platform's diversity.

- **Customizable dashboards:** Dashboards displaying key sustainability metrics, project outcomes, and collaboration indicators could offer stakeholders a snapshot of ongoing activities, enabling progress monitoring. Here, alignment with a future Observatory and the recently launched EC food systems dashboard is then needed.

As the Knowledge Hub evolves, future activities might include developing and integrating tailored tools and resources to meet the specific needs of stakeholders. Potential additions could include:

- **Interactive platforms:** Digital tools could enhance collaboration, such as matchmaking systems connecting stakeholders based on shared interests or objectives.
- **Educational modules:** Resources aimed at building capacity within the food system sector might range from technical training to workshops focused on policy development.
- **Case study repository:** A comprehensive database of successful initiatives and best practices could be a reference and inspiration for stakeholders across Europe.

These initiatives could strengthen stakeholder engagement, encourage knowledge-sharing, and support the transition toward more sustainable food systems.

6.1. The Knowledge Hub Startup Award

A flagship initiative for the Knowledge Hub could be the Startup Award, an annual program aimed at recognizing and supporting groundbreaking innovations within the food system sector. By identifying and promoting impactful startups, this award could foster innovative solutions to address pressing food system challenges.

The Knowledge Hub Startup Award is envisioned as an annual flagship initiative designed to foster groundbreaking innovations within the food system sector. The program aims to address critical challenges and pave the way for a more sustainable, inclusive, and resilient food system across Europe by identifying, promoting, and supporting promising startups. With the support of National Food Technology Platforms (NFTPs), this initiative seeks to bridge the gap between innovation and implementation, creating opportunities for collaboration, investment, and knowledge exchange.

To maximize its impact and inclusivity, the initiative foresees both European Awards and Local Awards, ensuring that entrepreneurs across European regions are widely motivated and engaged. The Local Awards would allow regional startups to gain visibility and recognition within their specific food system contexts, while the European Awards would highlight the most scalable and transformative solutions at a continental level. This dual approach ensures that both grassroots innovations and high-impact scalable models are acknowledged and supported, fostering a more interconnected and dynamic innovation ecosystem.

Objectives

The primary goal of the Startup Award is to unleash transformative potential and catalyze innovative solutions that tackle pressing food system issues, such as sustainability, food security, waste reduction, and digital transformation. By leveraging the extensive network of NFTPs, the program aspires to:

1. **Promote impactful innovations and sustainable value creation:** Recognize and reward startups developing transformative solutions for the food system.
2. **Foster collaboration:** Connect startups with key industry stakeholders, research networks, and investors.
3. **Scale successful models:** Provide platforms and resources to scale region-specific innovations (technological, organizational and social) to broader European and global contexts.

Key features

- The initiative could be widely promoted through NFTP's, potentially ensuring maximum visibility across diverse European regions and food system sectors.
- Dedicated campaigns might target startups, academic spin-offs, and innovators, encouraging their participation.

Evaluation

- A multidisciplinary jury, comprising experts from academia, industry, and policymaking, could evaluate submissions based on their innovation potential, scalability, and sustainability impact. Startups might also have the opportunity to present their solutions and respond to questions from the jury, ensuring a fair and transparent evaluation process.
- The selection process could emphasize inclusivity, aiming for diverse geographical and thematic representation among participants. This might be achieved through targeted outreach, transparent evaluation criteria, and the involvement of diverse stakeholders in the selection process.

Award categories

- Innovations for environmental sustainability
- Digital transformation in food Systems
- Advancements in nutrition and health
- Circular economy solutions
- Cross-cutting innovations

Role of National Food Technology Platforms (NFTPs)

NFTP's would play a pivotal role in ensuring the Startup Award's success. Their contributions include:

- **Promotion and outreach:** Engaging with startups at the national level to encourage participation and ensure a diverse pool of applicants.
- **Networking support:** Facilitating connections between startups and local industry stakeholders, investors, and policymakers.
- **Regional representation:** Providing insights and feedback on regional challenges and opportunities to guide the program's focus.

The Startup Award could serve as a catalyst for accelerating the transition toward sustainable food systems by identifying and supporting transformative solutions. The initiative would have the potential to strengthen collaboration networks spanning academia, industry, and policymakers. With financial, technical, and networking support, startups might gain the necessary resources to effectively scale their solutions.

The Knowledge Hub Startup Award could represent a significant opportunity to align innovation with sustainability objectives, empowering startups to address Europe's most critical food system challenges. By leveraging the expertise and networks of NFTP's, this initiative might create a dynamic platform for collaboration, investment, and growth, paving the way for a more sustainable and resilient future.

7. Dissemination activities conducted in 2024

In 2024, significant dissemination efforts were undertaken to support the development and promotion of the Knowledge Hub within the FOODPathS initiative. These activities aimed to increase awareness, foster stakeholder engagement, and showcase the potential of the Hub to transform food systems across Europe. By leveraging high-profile events, webinars, and targeted collaborations, the dissemination

strategy focused on connecting diverse stakeholders, sharing best practices, and promoting the integration of the Knowledge Hub into existing networks and initiatives.

The following highlights detail the key dissemination events and activities that contributed to advancing the Knowledge Hub's objectives (see *Annex III for pictures of the dissemination events*).

French Foodtech network, 1st February 2024 (120 participants)

During their annual event, ANIA exhibited a roll-up of the FOODPathS project and shared leaflets and information with French food startups.

ALIMENTARIA, 20 March 2024 (30 participants)

FIAB organized and celebrated FOODpathS event in the frame of FIAB conferences, [ALIBER](#), in Alimentaria Barcelona March 2024. ([Programme ALIBER 2024](#))

The session focused on Sustainability, Food Waste, Food Safety, and New Protein, mainly, as model of partnership for sustainable food systems, including different presentations starting with FOODPathS presentation (by INRAE), challenges and solutions for engaging private partners in the SFS (by FDE), suggestion for the ideal partnership (by Confagricoltura), presentation of HUB of Living Labs (by ANIA), modus operandi [FoodforLife-Spain](#) (by FIAB) and different European projects focusing the transformation of food systems towards healthy and sustainability. ([Insights from ALIMENTARIA Barcelona 2024](#))

NFTPs meeting in Barcelona, 19 March 2024

FOODPathS Knowledge Hub was disseminated.

Conference at SIAL for the official launch of the platform, 21st October 2024 (50 participants)

After INRAE's introduction to FOODPathS project, ANIA presented the [Living Labs platform](#) to promote the exchange of best practices.

Following INRAE's presentation of the FOODPathS project, ANIA presented the Living Labs platform aimed at promoting the exchange of best practices.

Digitalfoodlabs presented the new edition of its report on the European food tech ecosystem and innovation.

Dr Daniele Rossi, Research and Innovation & VC, [Confagricoltura](#) & [FoodDrinkEurope](#) Delegate, highlighted National Food Technology Platforms (NFTPs) strategies to capitalise on existing networks and link the FOODPathS platform with living labs, with his presentation on *FOODPathS Living Lab Platform:NFTPs support*

Claude Yven, FutureFoodS partnership coordinator at the Agence Nationale de la Recherche, presented the extension of the FOODPathS project to FutureFoodS calls.

From the discussions and questions, it became apparent that the launch of the platform was warmly welcomed.

ALIBETOPIAS 2024, 24 October 2024 (350 participants)

FIAB organized and celebrated a new edition of its annual RDI Living Lab event, [ALIBETOPIAS](#), event for the agrifood sector in Spain. Finding practical solutions, generating thematic knowledge and new business collaboration. FIAB invited in its new edition top-level speakers linked to the sector, who shared the latest trends in RDI, and exhibitors had the chance to share new ideas, projects and results in a participative and collaborative environment. Celebrated on 24th October in Madrid, the event was attended by 350 stakeholders, including representatives from the food industry, academia, research institutions, and policymakers. Organized by the [Spanish Food and Drink Federation \(FIAB\)](#) and supported by the [Technological Platform Food for Life Spain](#) and the [Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, and Food](#), this 10th-anniversary edition focused on advancing the future of food and drink in Spain through collaboration, innovation, and sustainability. The event demonstrated the Living Lab approach, showcasing the FOODPathS Living Labs platform, which includes cases from across Europe that aim to collaboratively develop, test, and scale sustainable food systems ([FOODPathS engages with the food sector at ALIBETOPÍAS 2024](#)).

NFTPs meeting in Bucharest, 29th October 2024

FIAB as coordinators of NFTPS, National Food Technology Platforms meetings, organized meeting in Bucharest on 29th October inviting FDE to present the HUB inviting all platforms and relevant

stakeholders invited to this meeting to participate and collaborate actively in FOODPathS Knowledge Hub.

FOODPathS Webinar: ‘Inspiring food systems cases’, 21 November 2024

In collaboration with [JPI HDHL](#), the webinar ‘[Inspiring Food Systems Cases](#)’ showcased transformative initiatives driving sustainability within European food systems. The session highlighted successful examples of food system practices that contribute to sustainable outcomes, engaging stakeholders across the food value chain.

FoodDrinkEurope presented insights on the role of public-private partnerships and Living Labs in fostering collaboration. She introduced the web mapping of Living Labs available through the Knowledge Hub platform, accessible at [FOODPathS Living Labs](#), emphasizing its role in supporting stakeholder engagement and knowledge sharing.

Webinar, 28 November 2024 (70 participants)

DigitalFoodLabs presented the [new trends of the French food tech ecosystem](#) and innovation through its new report, sponsored by the FOODPathS project. ANIA introduced the project, the living lab platform, and the FutureFoodS call.

8. Conclusion

The FOODPathS Knowledge Hub represents a major step forward in fostering collaboration and innovation to address the pressing challenges of Europe’s food systems. By connecting stakeholders from research, policy, education, and industry, the Hub has the potential to become a central platform for sharing knowledge, exchanging best practices, and driving sustainable transformation.

A key achievement thus far has been the creation of the [Foodtech Living Labs Platform](#), which connects national and regional Food Systems Living Labs (FS-Labs) across Europe. This platform facilitates the exchange of insights and successful models, paving the way for scalable and adaptable solutions. This effort marks the beginning of the Knowledge Hub’s development, laying the groundwork for a collaborative and inclusive space.

While the Knowledge Hub shows significant promise, potential barriers to its further development and adoption must be addressed. Fragmentation within the existing landscape of initiatives could pose a challenge, as stakeholders may struggle to navigate and integrate into the Hub. Ensuring the platform’s accessibility and user-friendliness is critical to overcoming this issue. Additionally, data-sharing agreements and governance mechanisms will need to be carefully structured to foster trust among stakeholders. Limited financial and human resources for maintaining and expanding the Hub could also hinder its progress, necessitating strong partnerships and sustainable funding models.

The Hub’s success depends on its ability to remain user-centered and responsive to stakeholder needs. Continued stakeholder engagement through surveys, workshops, and collaborative projects will be crucial for refining its functionalities. Proposed initiatives such as the Startup Award demonstrate how the Hub can promote innovation while strengthening networks across academia and industry. The Hub’s adaptability and focus on cross-sectoral collaboration position it as a valuable resource for addressing interconnected challenges like climate resilience, digital innovation, and food security.

The finalized prototype of the Knowledge Hub will be presented at the [FOODPathS Festival](#) in Brussels from May 20–22, 2025. Following its initial introduction at SIAL Paris in October 2024, this event will provide an opportunity to showcase its expanded functionalities, highlight refinements based on stakeholder feedback, and further strengthen its role in fostering collaboration and innovation across Europe’s food systems.

By connecting diverse actors, the Knowledge Hub aims to drive meaningful and actionable change, fostering a resilient and sustainable food system for the future.

9. Recommendations

The FOODPathS Knowledge Hub has the potential to become a central resource for fostering collaboration, knowledge exchange, and innovation across Europe’s food systems. To maximize its impact

and ensure its long-term relevance, several key recommendations should be considered for policymakers, FutureFoodS, and other collaborative initiatives.

- **Strengthening the role of National Food Technology Platforms (NFTPs)**

To enhance the effectiveness of the Knowledge Hub, it is strongly recommended to reinvest in NFTPs and clarify their role within the European food ecosystem. NFTPs should be positioned as key facilitators in visualizing and integrating the broad range of food system initiatives across Europe. Their contributions should include strengthening links between research, industry, and policy, promoting national and local food heritage within broader European sustainability objectives, and facilitating the exchange of best practices while scaling successful models across regions. NFTPs can act as essential intermediaries, ensuring that regional perspectives are integrated into European food policies and research agendas.

- **Enhancing stakeholder engagement and dynamic content management**

To maintain the relevance and utility of the Knowledge Hub, it is strongly recommended to establish a system for periodic stakeholder input collection. Regular surveys and consultations should be conducted to ensure the platform remains dynamic, user-centric, and up-to-date. Furthermore, integrating this feedback loop into future food system programs will help align ongoing research, policies, and innovation efforts with real-world needs.

- **Addressing fragmentation and enhancing integration**

One of the main challenges in the food systems landscape is the fragmentation of existing initiatives. Instead of creating entirely new structures, the Knowledge Hub should prioritize consolidating and integrating existing initiatives to provide a cohesive and easily accessible platform.

- **Creating a comprehensive and accessible repository**

The Knowledge Hub should serve as a central repository for European projects, functioning as a one-stop-shop where stakeholders, including SMEs and farmers, can access best practices, tools, and collaborative opportunities. To further enhance engagement, an annual meeting should be organized to foster collaboration, facilitate networking, and encourage knowledge sharing among different actors within the food system.

- **Engaging citizens and promoting public consultations**

Public consultations should not be limited to industry stakeholders but should also actively involve citizens. Consumers' perceptions and societal expectations play a crucial role in shaping food innovations, and their inclusion in early-stage discussions could help align research and policy with real-world needs. Co-creation sessions within Food Systems Living Labs could also harness citizen creativity, leading to more inclusive and socially accepted innovations.

- **Using the Knowledge Hub to operationalize RIPE priorities**

The RIPE framework addresses “what” questions concerning sustainable food system transformation, while the Knowledge Hub should focus on the “how.” This means the platform should not only present knowledge but also provide clear, practical pathways for implementing RIPE-driven strategies. Strengthening connections between research, policy, and education through structured frameworks and interactive tools will be key to operationalizing these concepts.

- **Supporting the Knowledge Hub Startup Award**

One of the most impactful initiatives proposed within the Knowledge Hub is the Startup Award, designed to support and promote innovation in the food system sector. This initiative should be strongly supported, as it has the potential to drive forward transformative solutions. The [Ecotrophelia Europe](#) has already demonstrated the power of such initiatives in engaging students, and the Knowledge Hub Startup Award could extend this concept to a wider range of food system actors. Furthermore, the initiative should be structured to include both European-level awards and local awards to ensure broader participation across regions.

- **Aligning with the pact for skills initiative**

Recognizing the importance of skills development within the food system sector, the Knowledge Hub should be closely linked to initiatives such as the Pact for Skills. This will ensure that stakeholders, ranging from industry professionals to farmers, have access to training programs that help bridge skills gaps and foster innovation. The Knowledge Hub could further enhance these efforts by integrating educational resources tailored to the needs of the food sector.

By implementing these recommendations, the Knowledge Hub can evolve into a central pillar for European food system innovation. It will provide a structured, inclusive, and accessible platform that bridges knowledge, policy, and practice to drive meaningful change. The Hub's success will ultimately depend on its ability to remain dynamic, adaptable, and aligned with the evolving needs of food system stakeholders across Europe.

Annexes

Annex I - Survey details

Survey: Developing the Knowledge Hub for Sustainable Food Systems

Introduction

FOODPathS is working to establish a Knowledge Hub to serve as a central platform for collaboration, innovation, and knowledge-sharing among stakeholders in the sustainable food systems community. The Hub will integrate best practices, tools, and resources from across Europe to address key challenges and opportunities in food systems.

We value your insights and feedback, which will help shape the development of this Knowledge Hub. Please take a few minutes to complete this survey. Your input will help us ensure the Hub meets users' needs and expectations.

Survey questions

Part 1: Understanding Your Needs

- 1. What types of resources or tools would you find most valuable in a Knowledge Hub?** *(Select up to 3)*
 - Case studies of successful projects
 - Research databases and reports
 - Networking opportunities with stakeholders
 - Training and capacity-building resources
 - Policy guidance and recommendations
 - Digital tools for collaboration
- 2. What areas of sustainable food systems should the Knowledge Hub prioritise?** *(Select all that apply)*
 - Innovation and technology
 - Education and training
 - Policy and Governance
 - Entrepreneurship and business development
 - Climate resilience and environmental sustainability

Part 2: Expectations for the Knowledge Hub

- 4. How would you prefer to engage with the Knowledge Hub?** *(Select all that apply)*
 - Interactive webinars and online workshops
 - Access to downloadable resources
 - Participating in forums or discussion groups
 - Receiving newsletters and updates
 - Contributing your own knowledge and experiences

5. **What do you think would make the Knowledge Hub stand out and provide unique value compared to other platforms?** (*Open question*)

Part 3: Collaboration and Feedback

7. **Do you have any additional suggestions or expectations for the Knowledge Hub?** (*Open question*)

If you are interested in FOODPathS, you can follow our activities on our [website](#), on LinkedIn and Twitter (looking for #FOODPathS or on @SciFoodHealth accounts), and on the [Sustainable Food Systems Network](#) community. You can also register to the FOODPathS database and receive information about news, events, publications, and opportunities coming from the project.

For information about our privacy practices, please read our Privacy policy [here](#).

You can unsubscribe at any time by clicking the link in the footer of our emails. You can also send an email to info@foodpaths.eu.

We use Mailchimp as our marketing platform. By clicking to subscribe, you acknowledge that your information will be transferred to Mailchimp for processing. [Learn more about Mailchimp's privacy practices here](#).

Annex II - Workshop details

Workshop 3: The Knowledge Hub of Food System Labs unites R&I, science-to-Policy and Education (RIPE)

The recently launched virtual Knowledge Hub of Food System Labs presents numerous examples of food system cases across Europe. These cases represent various orientations, including research-, innovation-, policy-, education-, entrepreneurship-, observatory- and networks. Some cases also highlight multiple orientations, reflecting the complexity of food systems. In this session, participants will work in groups to explore whether these different orientations converge or diverge in the topics they address. The goal is to generate a set of recommendations that will guide the further development of the RIPE and strengthen the Knowledge Hub. This collaborative effort will help identify synergies, gaps, and potential new cases that can be included to ensure the Hub remains a valuable resource for driving sustainable food systems forward.

Time: 2 hours (13.30-15.30)

Date: December 4 2024

Number of groups: 4 (8-10 people per group)

Questions for the discussion

1. How can the complexity of food systems be considered in the organization and provision of science advice to policy makers?
2. How can Policymakers facilitate regulations and foster dialogue between regulators (e.g., EFSA) and Research and Innovation and Education (and companies) to facilitate the solution of above issues?
3. Would training in serious games help FS actors to collective change our pathways?
4. What specific resources or tools would make the Knowledge Hub a valuable asset for your work within the food system?

Additional questions

1

- How can re-thinking the traditional linear and mono-disciplinary science advice to co-creation process and linked thematic science advice?
- Which types of science to policy advice may support the policies aiming at transition of European food systems?

2

- Which knowledge and which skills are mostly needed to be taught to achieve a sustainable SFS talent pool and how can this best be organized?
- How can serious (educational) games help FS actors to collective change our pathways?

3

- Which policies could serve a new SFS framework (playing field & boundaries) that guarantees that all, interacting, food systems respect the healthy planet conditions?
- What kind of solutions in FS do you propose that may keep us between the planetary and societal limits?

4

- How can the Knowledge Hub enhance collaboration across Research & Innovation, Policy, and Education within food systems?
- What mechanisms (e.g., peer-reviewed uploads, open-access platforms, webinars) would make sharing and accessing information more efficient?

Annex III - Dissemination events

Dissemination events in 2024

Figure 5 - French Foodtech network, 1st February 2024

Figure 4- French Foodtech network, 1st February 2024

Figure 6 – Alimentaria, 20 March 2024

Figure 7 - Conference at SIAL for the official launch of the platform, 21st October 2024

Figure 8 – ALIBETOPIAS, 24 October 2024

Figure 9- FOODPaths dissemination in exhibitors space, ALIBETOPIAS, 24 October 2024

webinar 21st November 2024, 11.00 - 12.15 CET

Inspiring food systems cases

Insights from initiatives that are transforming Europe

Register now!

Figure 10 - FOODPathS Webinar: 'Inspiring food systems cases', 21 November 2024

WEBINAR

État de l'écosystème d'innovation FoodTech & perspectives pour 2025

Jeudi 28 novembre - 14h00

 DigitalFoodLab
BE PART OF THE FUTURE

Figure 11 - Webinar, 28 November 2024

foodpaths